

Koreans

Data source: eHRAF

By Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

* Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.

Entry tags: Religion, Korean Religions, Korean Confucianism, Korean Shamanism

This entry focus on Sondup'o village of Samku Li town, located on Ganghwa Island, Korea (now South Korea), as a representation of a typical Korean village community ca. 1947. The inhabitants of Sondup'o do not have a formal, organized religion but rather a practice of ancestor worship (with roots in Shamanism) influenced by Confucianism and Buddhism. This spiritual ideology permeates most aspects of life, so the society is best characterized as coterminous with the religious group.

Date Range: 1925 CE - 1950 CE

Region: Ganghwa Island, South Korea

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, Republic of Korea

This entry focuses on Sondup'o village, of Samku Li town, on Ganghwa Island, Korea (now South Korea), ca. 1940. The region is now known as Seondu-Ri, Ganghwa Island, South Korea.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=aa01-000>.

– Source 1 Description: Kim, C. S., & Skoggard, I. A. (1998). Culture Summary: Korea. New Haven, Conn.: HRAF.

– Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=aa01-022>

– Source 2 Description: Osgood, C. (1951). Koreans And Their Culture. New York: The Ronald Press Company.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "Christianity, which has had a remarkable impact on Korea [referring to what is now South Korea], has made itself felt in the local scene since the beginning of the century" (Osgood, 1951:128). Despite having contact with the religion of Christianity, "it is clear that Christianity has had little effect on Sondup'o [focal village] which must be described as a Confucian village" (Osgood, 1951:129).

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: "Spirit worship, the oldest of Korean religious patterns, still obtains some deferential recognition from the farming populace despite various efforts to stamp it out, the most recent being that by the Japanese. Again, the external manifestations may be prohibited under penalty, but once the pressure of punishments is lifted, the ancient ideas produce behavior that education alone can eliminate" (Osgood, 1951:122-123).

– Yes

Notes: "The advent of both Confucianism and Buddhism brought about periodic official repressions of Shamanism but the latter also left its mark on both. The animal festivals reported in connection with Buddhism in the tenth century are one of the possible influences. Buddhism was tolerant, too much so for its own purity. The intelligent early Yi kings attacked religious superstitions of all faiths and we find various occasions when shamanistic practitioners were prohibited from the capital. In 1413, for example, all the practitioners of Shamanism were ordered to deliver up their books, which were then burned. Even as late as 1893, however, the Korean queen was so respectful of the mutang [female shamans] that she elevated one to the rank of princess, at the same time banishing a man to Cheju Island for protesting" (Osgood, 1951:246).

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare, indicates that "internal warfare seems to occur almost constantly and at any time of the year." Additionally, SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, indicates that the society is "not pacified for all or part of the twenty-five-year time period." Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare, indicates that "external warfare seems to occur almost constantly and at any time of the year." Additionally, SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, indicates that the society is "not pacified for all or part of the twenty-five-year time period." Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The focal community does not have a formal, organized religion that could be recognized by the government.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: "The religious participation of the people of Sondup'o [focus village] itself, apart from periodic worship at the ancestor tablets, proves uncertain and irregular. There is no formal study of Confucianism and there are no avowed Buddhists and, according to one opinion, few if any in the whole li. This, of course, does not prevent a crowd of people, particularly women and children, from attending the important annual feasts at the temple of Chondung" (Osgood, 1951:128).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 800

Notes: "...the village contained somewhat less than two hundred people, that almost all the families were nominally Confucianists" (Osgood, 1951:11-12). About 800 people live in the town of Samku Li, and 169 in the village of Sondup'o village (Osgood, 1951:24).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 100

Notes: "...the village contained somewhat less than two hundred people, that almost all the families were nominally Confucianists" (Osgood, 1951:11-12). About 800 people live in the town of Samku Li, and 169 in the village of Sondup'o village (Osgood, 1951:24).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Intimately connected with the collective spirit world are the mutang or female shamans, the high priestesses of the formalized cult of spirit worship which has survived from primitive prehistoric days. At least one mutang lives in the town of Samku Li...But as far as could be ascertained, there are no professionals in the villages of Sondu Ri" (Osgood, 1951:128).

Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: The mutang, or female shaman "will establish helpful, or at least informative, communication with her spirit associates for a fee consistent with one's ability to pay. In this way one may circumvent malevolent spirits causing disease or other difficulties, or perhaps get in touch with a relative who has recently departed from the world of more ordinary conversations. Shamans pay obeisance to innumerable spirit deities..." (Osgood, 1951:128).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: The religion of the the focal village in Korea (now South Korea) is best characterized as a mix of Shamanism (or Spirit/Ancestor Worship) and Confucianism, with Buddhist influences. There are no sacred texts associated with this unique belief system. (see Osgood, 1951: 245-247).

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Religious architecture is not listed as a type of large or impressive structure present in the focal community (Murdock and Wilson, 1972). However, on the island of Ganghwa, temples are present. "On southern Kanghwa is situated one of Korea's most famous Buddhist sites, the fortified monastery of Chondung Sa, nestled behind ancient stone walls in a pocket formed by three hills some hundreds of feet high. This relic of past glory was occupied only by the abbot, two priests, a nun, and a few lay servants" (Osgood, 1951:10-11).

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: See Osgood, 1951:115-117.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "Two days following the death, the unwashed body of the dead man, dressed in his best garments with special paper shoes, is tied in seven places with hemp rope as he lies stretched out on his back with his hands, palms down, on his pelvis. The tyings are correlated with the seven stars of the Constellation of the Bear, which Koreans consider lucky. Relatives place the body on a plank which rests on two wood pillows in the lower end of the room, which is to say, the most honored position nearest the fire. Then they add a folding screen in front. When the coffin has been completed, men bring it into the room where the dead man rests and, lifting him by the feet and shoulders, tuck him into it on a loose mattress of dike grass. More grass is added over the body and the flat cover is fastened down with slanting pegs" (Osgood, 1951:116).

Cremation:

– No

Notes: "People in Sondup'o [focal village] have heard of cremation and there may have been a case or two in the area, perhaps as the result of Japanese influence, but they do not remember them" (Osgood, 1951:118).

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "Two days following the death, the unwashed body of the dead man, dressed in his best garments with special paper shoes, is tied in seven places with hemp rope as he lies stretched out on his back with his hands, palms down, on his pelvis. The tyings are correlated with the seven stars of the Constellation of the Bear, which Koreans consider lucky. Relatives place the body on a plank which rests on two wood pillows in the lower end of the room, which is to say, the most honored position nearest the fire. Then they add a folding screen in front. When the coffin has been completed, men bring it into the room where the dead man rests and, lifting him by the feet and shoulders, tuck him into it on a loose mattress of dike grass. More grass is added over the body and the flat cover is fastened down with slanting pegs" (Osgood, 1951:116).

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: (Osgood, 1951:116)

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variables 1850 and 1852, secondary bone/body treatment is only present in a minority of cases (Schroeder, 2001; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: The principal ethnographic authority (Osgood, 1951) does not record any evidence for the presence of co-sacrifices in burials (see pages 115-119 for a description of a typical burial).

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: The principal ethnographic authority (Osgood, 1951) does not record any evidence for the presence of grave goods (see pages 115-119 for a description of a typical burial).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: See Osgood, 1951, various pages including 115-118, 151, 245-6.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: "On the morning of the funeral, the son sends several young men to dig the grave. If, as is usual, this is to be in the community cemetery, the boys choose a sunny place with as few roots and stones as possible so as not to make their labor more arduous than necessary. Formerly, when there were less restrictions on burials, a geomancer would have been consulted to determine a lucky location but this ancient custom has almost disappeared" (Osgood, 1951:116).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "Korean animism seems to focalize on some half a dozen conglomerations or groups of spirits. There are those, for example, which cluster around the house and are attached to its parts or juxtaposed constructions. There are the spirits of old trees, the spirits of mountains and other elements of the terrain, and the spirits of water and the sea. Finally, there are the more personal spirits which may be divided into two principal categories, the heroes of heaven, ranging from deities to the immortalized great whom time has hallowed, and unnamed uncertain spirits of the unhappy dead who haunt dark places to find both vengeance and escape by preying on the careless villager" (Osgood, 1951:122-123). However, the author continued to note that, "by and large, the present population of Sondu Ri show little interest in most of these spirits most of the time. Their attitude may be partly influenced by the fact that in this period of history they have more realistic fears for their personal happiness and security. Also, during the Japanese regime, the educational level of the younger generations was unquestionably raised. Under such circumstances, the acquisition of controlled information becomes most difficult" (ibid).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: A high god is absent or not reported in substantial descriptions of religious beliefs (SCCS variable 238; Ethnographic Atlas Column 34) (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Less distinctive spirits inhabit Korea in large numbers, although perhaps they are becoming more and more nebulous with the passing of time. Among them are the spirits of the recent dead. The funeral bell is rung to scare them away, but informants state they may return despite such prophylactic measures. Some persons claim not to be afraid of these disembodied souls" (Osgood, 1951:127).

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The New Year's feast is a ceremony "in honor of the last three generations of deceased direct male antecedents, including their wives...A table is placed in front of a cabinet with the ancestor tablet in it. Women put rows of ceremonial dishes with high

pedestal bases containing food on this table. The rear line of offerings should comprise harvest grains; in front of the grains are fish, meats, fruits, polished nuts, and other items according to taste and opportunity" (Osgood, 1951:119-122). It is not clear if food is offered as a symbol of respect, or to satisfy the hunger of human spirits.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Korean animism seems to focalize on some half a dozen conglomerations or groups of spirits. There are those, for example, which cluster around the house and are attached to its parts or juxtaposed constructions. There are the spirits of old trees, the spirits of mountains and other elements of the terrain, and the spirits of water and the sea. Finally, there are the more personal spirits which may be divided into two principal categories, the heroes of heaven, ranging from deities to the immortalized great whom time has hallowed, and unnamed uncertain spirits of the unhappy dead who haunt dark places to find both vengeance and escape by preying on the careless villager" (Osgood, 1951:122-123).

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: See Osgood, 1951:123.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Association with places and natural elements

Notes: "Mountains, like trees, command the respect of the people and the spirits of the innumerable surrounding hills are regarded as of a superior order. The embodiment of the mountain spirit is the tiger and it is said that if a bad man climbs the heights, the tiger will eat him" (Osgood, 1951:124). "Another category comprises the spirits of the sea or any body of water, including even a marsh" (Osgood, 1951:125-126).

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: For Example: "Fundamental to the Confucian philosophy is the notion that a good life depends upon a knowledge and observance of the proper behavior between one individual and another. Five categories of interpersonal relations form the basis for instruction as to the duties and obligations involved. These relations are those (1) of parent and child, (2) of king and minister, (3) of husband and wife, (4) of elder brother and younger brother, and (5) of friend with friend. Ideally, the approach demands a mutual attitude of benevolence, high-mindedness, restraint, understanding, and faith" (Osgood, 1951:38-39).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: "The religious participation of the people of Sondup'o [focus village] itself, apart from periodic worship at the ancestor tablets, proves uncertain and irregular. There is no formal study of Confucianism and there are no avowed Buddhists and, according to one opinion, few if any in the whole li. This, of course, does not prevent a crowd of people, particularly women and children, from attending the important annual feasts at the temple of Chondung" (Osgood, 1951:128).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: While participation in ancestor worship and mourning rituals is not required, it is practiced by the majority of the community. "For the first two years after a man's death, rice, soup, and wine, if possible, are placed before the ancestor tablet on the first and fifteenth day of each month and the wife or daughter wails. Then they remove the food and eat it" (Osgood, 1951:119).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Notes: Participation in the following ceremony is not required, but is a common practice for most members of the community. "The principal ceremonial occasions of the year have a direct connection with mourning. The New Year's feast, for example, is essentially a ceremony in honor of the last three generations of deceased direct male antecedents, including their wives. It is held on the first day of the first month at the house of the eldest member of the common lineage. In a formal sense, only men of the clan gather, but women may come to help in the preparation of the food. The proceedings vary from simple to complex according to family wealth and custom..." (Osgood, 1951:119-120).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: The Koreans are best described as a state. Note that the Ethnographic Atlas codes Koreans as having two levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, and a state usually has 3-4 levels (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). However, SCCS Variable 83 indicates that the Koreans have 3 or more hierarchical levels (Tuden, Arthur, and Marshall, 1972; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). See Osgood, 1951, pages 5-6, 20, for a detailed description of Korean political organization.

Education

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

— Yes

Notes: "About 1911, the English Episcopalian Mission on Kanghwa Island started a school in Kilsang My on which at least one boy in Sondup'o attended to obvious advantage. In May, 1920, the first public primary school opened in Samku Li under Japanese supervision and it has been operating ever since. Theoretically, every child in Sondup'o between the ages of six and twelve attends, although only fourteen are said to have been graduated up to 1947. Two of these have been able to continue their education in Seoul" (Osgood, 1951:101).

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

— Yes

Notes: "In May, 1920, the first public primary school opened in Samku Li under Japanese supervision and it has been operating ever since. Theoretically, every child in Sondup'o between the ages of six and twelve attends, although only fourteen are said to have been graduated up to 1947. Two of these have been able to continue their education in Seoul" (Osgood, 1951:101).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

— No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

— Yes

Notes: Because religion permeates almost every aspect of life, the religious group is best characterized as coterminous with society. The Koreans rely on "intensive cultivation where it is largely dependent upon irrigation" (Ethnographic Atlas [Murdock, 1962-1971], retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variable 232).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

— No

Notes: Transportation infrastructure is not intensively developed. "Not even a cart road connected this isolated settlement with the rest of the country" (Osgood, 1951:11). "Until modern times, the Han River was the route of communication with Seoul. Now there are antiquated buses on a gravel road which extends from the latter city northwest about thirty-five miles to the ferry crossing connecting with the

village of Kapkan Ri, port of Kanghwa City which lies still another three miles inland" (Osgood, 1951:18).

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Notes: Transportation infrastructure is not intensively developed. While it is present, it is not provided by a specific institution. "Not even a cart road connected this isolated settlement with the rest of the country" (Osgood, 1951:11). "Until modern times, the Han River was the route of communication with Seoul. Now there are antiquated buses on a gravel road which extends from the latter city northwest about thirty-five miles to the ferry crossing connecting with the village of Kapkan Ri, port of Kanghwa City which lies still another three miles inland. Besides the road to Kanghwa City from Kapkan Ri, the most important highway runs some ten miles to connect the island capital with Samku Li, or Three Roads Village, the principal town in the south, and by extension with the second ferry port of Ch'oji. Normally, there is a bus line on this route but since the war it has been periodically suspended. The north-south road actually comprises the eastern segment of a highway which loops around the island and provides adequate passage for an automobile except in the rainy season. There are numerous other roads orienting out from the capital, not to mention minor lanes which can almost imperceptibly disappear into narrowing rice dikes" (Osgood, 1951:18).

Taxation

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: Local Korean officials enforce a collection of grain for the government, in addition to government taxes (See Osgood, 1951:57-60).

Enforcement

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: There is a national, government police force in Korea (now South Korea). See Osgood, 1951, pages 21-23

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

— No

Notes: "Literacy is definitely increasing [as a result of the establishment of Mission schools], but of the twenty-seven family heads [in the focal village], only six are said by their peers to be able to read and write both the Chinese and onmun characters, which is the classical standard" (Osgood, 1951:101).

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Primary schools (under Japanese and Missionary supervision) provide lessons in Chinese and onmun characters. Additionally, the national language of Korea (now South Korea) is Korean (see Osgood, 1951:101-102).

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The national language of Korea (now South Korea) is Korean (see Osgood, 1951:101-102).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The people of Sondup'o village rely primarily on agriculture (rice being the most important crop), with fishing, hunting, and animal husbandry providing secondary sources of subsistence. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The people of Sondup'o village rely primarily on agriculture (rice being the most important crop), with fishing, hunting, and animal husbandry providing secondary sources of subsistence. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.